

NOTES

Composition of Cobalt-Diethyldithiocarbamate

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The formula of the complex cobalt diethyldithiocarbamate has been determined by (a) the method of continuous variations¹ (b) the slope ratio method² and (c) the mole ratio method³. The wavelength of maximum absorbance was determined by taking a known amount of cobalt sulphate to which an excess of sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (NaDDC) was added. The wavelength for maximum absorbance was found to be 385 m μ . The solutions used for different methods are shown below :

Method	CoSO ₄	NaDDC
(a)	0.002M	0.002M
	0.001M	0.001M
(b)	0.002M	0.02M
	0.02M	0.002M
(c)	0.002M	0.002M
	0.001M	0.001M

In method (c), 0.7 ml. CoSO₄ was taken in every case. The results are shown graphically in figures 1 to 3.

1. Job, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, X, 9, 113; 1936, XI, 6, 97.
2. Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488.
3. Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.

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Fig. 1 shows that the maximum absorbance corresponds to 1 : 3 of CoSO₄ : NaDDC, indicating the formula of cobalt diethyldithiocarbamate as Co(DDC)₃. This is supported by fig. 3. On the other hand, the ratio of the two slopes (fig. 2) is less than 1 : 3.

When CoSO₄ is in excess, there is a chance of a lower complex with a different λ_{\max} being formed, which may affect the value of the slope. Regenss⁴ has observed in case of cobalt-dipropyldithiocarbamate that the complex has the composition 1:2 or 1:3. It appears that a 1 : 2 complex of cobalt with DDC might have been formed in this case.

An attempt to study the effect of pH on the stability of the complex was not successful, since the solutions become turbid after some time, in presence of different buffers.

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